

Displacement from FATA Pakistan (2009-2016): Issues and Challenges

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Abstract

The Federally Administered Tribal Area (FATA) of Pakistan is a neglected region as far as development is concerned. It has been the hub of various illegal activities, including militancy and export of terrorism. Thus, it became inevitable for the government of Pakistan to act against militants through military operations. Over the years, hundreds of thousands of people have been fled FATA due to conflicts. Moreover, the military operation Zarb-e-Azb washas been launched in North Waziristan Agency in June 2014. Apart from its success, the operation displaced around 0.5 million people. This paper evaluates how the influx of these Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in the country is affecting the socio-economic situation. Secondly, the impact of such a huge number of displaced population on the law and order and security situation in the host areas is assessed.

Key Words: Af-Pak, Federally Administered Tribal Area, IDPs, Internal Displacement, Pakistan, Challenges, Issues

Introduction

Since 2001, Pakistan's alignment with the US has cost in a rising trend of increasing militancy within and across the border. To add to its complexity, initiatives taken by the government of Pakistan to abolish this menace from the national fabric enraged the locals and contributed in catalyzing ethnic and separatist movements. This has not only affected the law and order situation but also resulted in a stagnant economy and ever-rising poverty as well. As a result of the War on Terror (WOT), many militant groups sprang up in Pakistan, consequently, militancy increased in the country. These militant groups made their presence felt strong via collaboration with the like-minded groups and individuals across the country. Resultantly, the Pakistani military had to take stringent actions against the militias to curb militancy emanating from areas situated inside the

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Western border of the country. Millions of people have been dislocated due to the conflict between militants and military along the Western border of Pakistan. Return of the displaced people from one area is replaced by the flight of masses from another area. Thus internal displacement became sort of a permanent feature of Pakistani polity over the past several years. This paper ponders over the issues related to the influx of the internally displaced persons in the country and their effects on the socioeconomic situation of not only the displaced people but that of the host areas as well. Secondly, attention has been paid to gauge the impact of such a huge number of displaced population on the law and order and security situation in the host areas.

According to the UN Guiding Principles on internal displacement, IDPs can be defined as,

“Persons who have been forced or obliged to flee or to leave their homes or places of habitual residence, in particular as a result of or in order to avoid the effects of armed conflict, situations of generalized violence, violations of human rights or natural or human-made disasters, and who have not crossed an internationally recognized state border” (Kälin, 2008).

On the one hand, this definition reflects the conditions and situations which justify the position of people fleeing an armed conflict from the area of their origin to protect their lives. While on the other, it makes government responsible to assume certain responsibilities pertinent to their socioeconomic needs. It also identifies a need to abandon all kinds of discriminatory behavior while carrying out a mission to their welfare, that is all displaced persons must be dealt equally regardless of their creed, caste, origin, and reason of their displacement. (Kälin, 2008). The IDPs right to humanitarian assistance and protection comes first and foremost. While analyzing the scenario for the displacement of people from the period of 2009-2015 in Pakistan, the researchers are going to get the readers go through the trends which made these people displaced and how it affected their lives and the socioeconomic and security situation of the host areas.

According to the UN report, in 2009 almost 3 million newly displaced people had been added in Pakistan amid conflict in Swat. It published its report exhibiting the plight of IDPs living in the host communities or in slums. It also highlighted that merely fleeing the conflict zones, did not help them to eschew conflicts pertinent to social, economic and security crisis in their day to day lives. They had to had encountered suicide attacks from then on state armed groups in the camps. In April 2009, suicide bombings killed 38 and injured hundreds of people in southern KP. It created an emergency situation on the supplies of food, shelter, mental and physical measures. A climate of uncertainty clouded the minds of the uprooted people to find out alternative ways for their refuge. (Rousselot, 2010)

The crisis continued to loom dark shadows on the social fabric of the country. It also became a cause of social mobilisation for ethnic communities to initiate

separatist movements against government for not ensuring their right to life. On-State Armed Groups(NSAGs)carried out several attacks on minorities which includes Shiite, Christian and Hindu communities to fail the government in its efforts to ensure peace and security.In the year2015 alone, religious minorities became a foremost target of militant groups, for instance, in one of suicide attacks, 15 Christians were killed and more than 70 people injured. Moreover, Shia Muslims were killed at larger scale in Karachi, Sindh, Shikarpur, Peshawar and Sindh. (IDMC, 2015)

The 2014 military operations against non-state armed groups compelled thousands of people to flee to North Waziristan and Khyber Agencies. By the end of 2014 almost 907,000 people displaced and the number increased to 1.56 million by July 2015. It speaks volumes for human atrocities and sufferings, where many succumbed to the militant and military actions, in this brief era. (Pakistan IDP Figures Analysis, 2015)

More than 1.8 million people were displaced in 2015, amid insurgency and counterinsurgency in Pakistan. However, they are now returning to their area of origin, Kurram Agency and FATA. A separatist movement, going on since 2005, in the southwestern province of Balochistan has also played a central role in aggrandizing the plight of locals and pushing them to flee to other areas of the country. According to UNHCR report, almost 275,000 people displaced in 2005, and till date, no durable policy has been made to settle the dispute. (IDMC, 2015) The skirmishes in north-west in 2008 contributed to displace more than 4.8 million, among them many returned to the areas of their origin. However, still a large number of people require assistance to resettle in their areas of origin. These people are leaving significant impacts on the socio-economic and security situation of the hosting areas. (Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) Operation in KP/FATA, 2014)

Socioeconomic and Security Situation

While analyzing the socio-security impacts, we tend to read both of the sides of the coin. First, how this situation has jolted the social and security patterns of IDPs. Secondly, how it has affected the social and security situation of host areas. The difference of culture, in most of the cases, leave its impacts on people, when they are to absorb in the new climate. Acclimatization to new space requires years. In case of IDPs, it is not difficult to understand that, people of FATA possess a striking culture to that of KP or Punjab. The annihilation to their hometowns and their belongings already had affected their nerves. Moreover, when it comes to compromise their privacy pertinent to their women's pardah, they could not compromise much. It has thus, forced the affluent ones to avail rented accommodation instead of living in camps largely for their cultural reasons. However, among them too, several people were too vulnerable to register

themselves amid lack of provision of documents left them with nothing, but to live in camps (IDMC, 2015).

Some argue that the main obstacle for IDPs to adapt to camp life is their apprehensions regarding their physical security other than living conditions. In 2014, non-state armed groups targeted government-run camps. In May 2014 a suicide bomber killed 4 people and more than 11 people got major injuries in a camp in Peshawar. In the same month, Togh Sarai IDP camp, which was hosting more than 7,000 people from Kurram and Orakzai agencies, was attacked by militants, in which four were wounded. Amid this situation, many IDPs left camps and only came back in June when government assured that security measures were improved then. These security measures too proved inadequate, and another attack on the camps of Khawaja Muhammad IDP camp at Hangu district in the month of September killed 4 people and injured countless others. This situation left IDPs in a perplexing situation to avoid government-run camps and rely on rented accommodations (Pakistan IDP Figures Analysis, 2015).

Ramifications of Displacement

Almost all situations affect society in one way or the other. Any military action to sabotage militants safe heavens disrupts the social and economic life, as it threatens the security of common native people as well. Though the social and economic life of the people too affected at a larger scale, however, three main areas of their social lives were exposed to dynamic changes i.e. education, health and better chances of livelihood.

We need to have a cursory look at the lives and history of people of FATA and KP before their displacement and after their displacement amid armed conflict. The purpose is to analyze what altering attitudes did it bring into the lives of IDPs. As, aforementioned, three basic areas; education, health and better livelihood, began to exhibit amelioration.

Moreover, FATA being neglected from federal government's meetings agenda for decades, displacement worked as a pretext for IDPs where they became exposed to the urban life. It contributed largely to raising awareness about their due rights. Displacement became, nonetheless, an eye opener for them to realize that what this traditional system has denied them so far. How the education, health facilities and better infrastructure development had been kept away from them by their societal and political authorities (Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) Operation in KP/FATA, 2014).

Additionally, issues emanated at different platforms when it comes to developing coordination among the different organization, specifically responsible for providing aid and support to the IDPs. One major issue which lashes out after each catastrophe in the chaotic situation is the absence of Standard Operating Procedures SOPs to deal with the crises. Pakistan lacked the history of chalking

out and maintenance of any defined policy pertinent to IDPs. Though with sufficient help from the UNHCR, the displacement situations have been managed, but lack of liaison among organizations for cooperation at different levels has been observed. As need arose, there was need to hire a large number of skilled labor to manage the situation but amid the policy and knowledge vacuum, unskilled labor was being hired which also became a cause of pillaging resources.

In addition, the ground-breaking realities pertinent to health care facilities revealed to the IDPs once they were uprooted from their areas of origin. The mortality rate which was high in their area, especially when it comes to women and children, was significantly low in urban areas due to comparatively good health facilities. It also revealed to them that basic lifesaving practices which were considered taboo in their areas are substantial for their health and quality of life. For instance, polio vaccination, and post-delivery courses for mother and child were never considered important for their health and thus practices to abandon and discourage these courses contributed largely for the deterioration of the said patients (Kronstadt, 2010). Moreover, once IDPs entered the camps or facilitation centers, government medical camps were established to carry out their complete check-ups. Through the medical examination, many facts unveiled that many IDPs were victims of water-borne diseases and Hepatitis B. Further investigation to their medical history disclosed, that medical facilities in FATA and North Waziristan region were present at far distant places and most of the people did not have access to it (Kronstadt, 2010). Here too, feudal lords had the option to go to urban places or abroad for their check-ups but poor had to rely on the ill-equipped doctors. To add more pain to this agony, poor infrastructure with ill-equipped doctors has further aggravated the health situation in these areas. Many IDPs had a high mortality rate as mostly the hospitals were not only located at a distant place but even if some patients made it to the hospital, then they had to face another challenge that at times doctors were not present or the required medical and lab facilities were non-existent to handle the patients. So, nonetheless, mostly IDPs made it known that they had to depend on untrained midwives or “*Hakeems*” for their welfare (FATA Research Centre, 2014). However, in urban areas, they could have better health facilities and most importantly the awareness of their rights to health, which was abstained from them for decades. Therefore, in one way or other this displacement worked as a blessing in disguise for them.

Moreover, while looking at the sources of livelihood of the people of FATA in general and North Waziristan in particular, most people were relying on agriculture, or clothing, or they were either technicians or electricians. Earnings were also made from tourism and marble industry. Working in small enterprises of arms and ammunition also supported them. Overall they had limited earning resources, and those too were eliminated amid ongoing conflict (FATA Research Centre, 2014). The government, however, started reconstruction of the markets and infrastructure but many showed their reservations to restart their businesses

because of the security situation. There were people who after losing their loved ones in the militancy and armed conflicts were so grieved that they left their cultivable lands and jobs and now were unwilling to go back.

However, when it comes to compensating IDPs for all the financial loss they incurred, the government authorities could not prove effective in resolving their concerns. According to IDPs, they did not only lost their loved ones, houses, and lands, but they also became handicapped when it finally came to provide basic necessities of life to their families amid lack of financial support and opportunities given to them by the authorities. They needed sustainable and secured jobs, which could help them and raise their living standards (Rousselot, 2010).

One way of resolving their concern was to provide technical education to the IDPs, whether even for a period of six months, and open avenues to help them start getting decent earnings. IDPs largely supported the steps taken by the government to increase mineral mining projects in FATA, because it helped increase their job opportunities. They also said, that with the mining projects, comes better infrastructure and best international practices. Moreover, the exposure to the international mining expertise drives local people to attain education.

The geological survey has revealed that FATA possesses 20 trillion cubic feet of gas. The government has issued a license to 15 blocs in FATA, which would prove as a relief for the locals, in the realm of improving their social and economic life (Dawn, 2016).

Impact on the Host Areas

Due to cultural and lingual similarity, it is rightly estimated that most of the displaced people from FATA prefer to live in KP. The operation in North Waziristan made Bannu, as the largest hosting district for the displaced. Moreover, Peshawar, D.I Khan, Tank, and Kohat also served a large number of people coming from North Waziristan. The influx of a large number of people doubled the population of Bannu from 563,000 to millions. This has resulted in socioeconomic and security situation (FATA Research Centre, 2014).

The socioeconomic situation of the host areas altered largely, as every hosting area has its spatial limit to absorb a large amount of population. In the case of the displaced people, the urban areas of Bannu, KP, Kohat, and Peshawar witnessed several difficulties related to the higher population densities. For instance, compared to the inhabitants of the urban population, people coming from remote areas possess larger family members (IDMC, 2015). Providing them accommodation on rent or even in camps becomes a daunting task, as most of the families insist to stay together. Provision of their livelihood, though for a trivial period of time, is also not an easy task to be carried out as urban areas already confront issues of high population. With time it has become a pressing problem in urban areas to provide employment opportunities to all the sections of the society.

Especially people coming from FATA and North Waziristan lacked the education and skills to be accommodated according to their skill set. Another major issue arises with the realization of the diversity of cultural norms being practiced by both host communities and IDPs.

Additionally, whenever the security situation is challenged in an area, it cripples or paralyzes the routine activities of daily life. The continuous militancy did not only damage security situation in FATA, North and South Waziristan agencies, but it also had a spill over effect to the hosting areas. According to a UNHCR report, the security situation of KP became precarious when a large number of IDPs arrived. During the investigations, it was revealed that many IDPs had connections with the militants. So, the safety and security of the camps were at stake and subsequently what was observed was that there were back to back attacks on the camps. With the abet of culprits housed in camps, it became easy targets of the militants. Many suspects, when they were brought under investigation, made a hue and cry. However, with necessary steps by the law enforcement agencies, the dust got settled with the passage of time (Basic Human Rights(bhr), 2012).

As the security situation in the host areas was also challenged, the burden to accommodate almost 1.7 million IDPs for their education, health and livelihood became a daunting task for the government authorities. However, not sufficiently though, many strategies were chalked out to provide them with a sustained environment for a trivial period of time. Nonetheless, one must not forget the challenge of resettling the IDPs in their areas of origin was a mammoth task.

Moreover, with the destruction of infrastructure in KP and FATA, the education system also became paralyzed and crippled. An air of fear further hindered students and teachers to join the schools. The major targets of militants for the last decade had been schools, camps, and hospitals for a significant period of time, so to make a huge impact. However, with the displacement, IDPs were on the contrary exposed to new opportunities of education for their children. Being low in the priority of federal governments, the education system in KP and FATA always needed a massive revamp. The increased number of Ghost schools and schools-cum drawing room of influential people had significantly contributed to increasing illiteracy rates in these areas. Most of the teachers were on government payroll, however, they never visited the school systems and continuously drew pay on fake documents (FATA Research Centre, 2014).

The IDPs used this displacement as an opportunity to equip their children with better education. Once they felt that there is a huge difference in the level of education i.e. what is provided to them in FATA and what kind of quality education is being imparted in urban areas, consequently, they felt motivated to ensure quality education for their children. Another major reason which somehow proved displacement beneficial for them was to realize the right of educating their girls, which had always been undermined by the strict cultural norms prevailing in

mostly rural areas of KP and the almost the whole of the FATA region. A large number of girls breathed their wish to get a better education (Mumtaz, 2009). Where, on the one hand, displacement produced incentives for displaced people, on the other, the social skeleton of host areas faced issues pertinent to overpopulation and limited means to meet needs of the IDPs.

Though that displacement proved a blessing in disguise for the dislocated people in the realm of the health sector. However, on the contrary, it posed a number of challenges for the host areas on many fronts. For instance, in health sector alone, where the government tried its best to establish and provide health centers, a number of challenges arose on the surface. The number of health centers in relation to the number of IDPs was insufficient to deliver adequate health care facilities. When the crisis hit, the health department had to face the influx of hundreds of IDPs on daily basis. There were colossal of trauma, anxiety and depression cases, which needed urgent and persistent medication and therapies. Sleeplessness was also recorded among the displaced ones (Basic Human Rights(bhr), 2012). Whilst in the middle of the situation, IDPs were mainly concerned about their future. As most people lost their loved ones in militancy and lost their kids during displacement. While surveys carried out by UNDP, it revealed that doctors emphasized on the need of increasing of not only the number of health centers and doctors but also ensures the availability of psychologists. However, huge hue and cry was observed in the beginning, but with the passage of time, it calmed down with the help of doctors and support from different UN agencies (Kronstadt, 2010)

Moreover, there were many instances where the IDPs exhibited dissatisfaction over the health facilities in KP and Balochistan. The fact behind all this crisis was not emanating from the negligence from the doctors/nurses, but the number of cases, which each health center had to deal with on the daily basis. According to a UNHCR report, the health infrastructure was not prepared for the influx of five million people. The public hospitals were, already, in deplorable condition, and with the arrival of displaced people, public hospitals reaffirmed its incapacity to handle the crisis. So, nonetheless, in extreme cases, IDPs were to depend on expensive hospitals and private clinics (Kronstadt, 2010).

In addition, many nuisances being reported where crime rate rose to a significant level. According to various reports, in 2014 the KP government admitted that law and order situation had been deteriorated with the arrival of IDPs. The cases of extortions, target killing, and grenade attacks had become a fashion and there was a need to evolve a framework to fill gaps in the policy to avoid human and infrastructure loss of KP and other hosting areas. As aforesaid the security and safety situation also being challenged as some IDPs had connections with the militants. Once revealed, they had been strangled by the authorities to avoid any further loss. However, the entire blame cannot be rested with IDPs, as in most cases, they themselves were the target of militancy (Ali, 2014).

Impact on the IDPs

IDPs are altogether the major sufferer in their journey from being uprooted from their area of origin to the camps of their temporary settlement. Where their dismal condition brought them at the threshold of hosting areas, it also became a source for them to be exposed to a new standard of living and opportunities, which they lacked back home. Not only had they confronted several issues, but improved standards of living made them optimistic to start their lives in cities, host areas, thus it influenced their lives largely.

The health facilities provided by the government authorities lacked potential to handle major injury cases. Mostly camps were established to provide first aid or urgent care. The serious cases, thus, were sent to the public hospitals, which were in deplorable condition. According to a UNHCR report, more than 260 patients from FATA were suffering from HIV in Hayatabad Medical Complex. Almost 161 men, 73 women and a significant number of children were reported to be the victim of this contagious disease. With the poor conditions of the camps and rising temperatures, and insufficient health facilities, many IDPs were to depend on private hospitals for a quick recovery. Moreover, there were more than 69,000 pregnant women in the camps, which needed urgent care (FATA Research Centre, 2014). In 2009, UNHCR reported heart-wrenching facts about increasing rates in HIV cases, and Hepatitis C virus patients. This rate grew amid illiteracy and lack of knowledge pertinent to the use of blades, blood transfusion, and dental surgeries. Little care has been carried out in rural areas when it comes to performing shave, dental surgeries, and blood transfusion without sterilizing the equipment. This is the reason that major victims of Hepatitis C virus were found in males, age between 1-60 years. Moreover, a move towards easy earning indulged many male and female members of the IDPs in offering sex to receive money in return, which also became a cause of the widespread of HIV and Aids. Some other causes for the increased spread of this disease lie in the fact of not reaching to the professional doctor for medical help. Few IDPs revealed that even with the diagnosis of their disease, many people believe in self-medication as they lack enough finances to treat themselves (Amnesty International, 2010).

As mentioned earlier, with the militancy and military operations, the existing infrastructure of educational and health facilities was badly damaged. It is reported that only 1/3rd of children had access to education, which subsequently reduced to the minimum with the continuous bombing from militants. Arriving at the hosting areas, the IDPs were provided with an opportunity to discover better education facilities but as it was for a trivial period of time, many IDPs preferred to look forward to staying in KP and hosting areas for the better future of their children (FATA Research Centre, 2014).

In addition, the plight of IDPs increased as they were to remain deprived of receiving assistance due to no availability of documents. As, their issues remained unaddressed pertinent to food, shelter, healthcare, and sanitation, have resulted in making them indulge in criminal activities to fulfil their needs by hook or crook. There has been observed an increase in male and female sex workers, which resultantly became a pretext for the increase in HIV and Aids in the society in latent years. This has largely contributed to deteriorating the law and order situation and the spread of immoral activities in the host areas.

Moreover, the lack of road infrastructure, where the camps were built also made it difficult for IDPs to reach to the NADRA offices for their registration and collecting their registration cards. Among undocumented IDPs, there were a large number of women and children, who were not registered because they did not have CNIC. Most of the women being illiterate did not understand its importance and were also stopped by their men to make one, as it required them to take a picture and go through a procedure which might need them to encounter male staff members of concerned NADRA offices (FATA Research Centre, 2014).

In addition, as most of the people from FATA, preferred to stay in KP, the climate conditions of hot weather in the host areas, also became unbearable for them. In the scorching heat of May, June, and July, people had to stay in camps. The temperature in most of the hosting areas of KP for the summer runs from 38-44degree Celsius. Moreover, lack of electricity in the camps and insufficient availability of water further aggravated the situation for the IDPs. These factors played a central role in the spread of diseases in children and women, amid malnutrition and lack of electricity, water, and food supply. According to a UNHCR report in 2009, there were more than 69,000 pregnant women among the displaced population, which were in dire need of proper health care. But due to lack of hospitals and healthcare centers in KP government-run camps, many children and women suffered irreversible losses. (Mumtaz, 2009)

Additionally, another major problem which grabbed the attention of many NGOs was the issue of human rights violation pertinent to the discriminatory behavior of the host communities and government authorities towards FATA IDPs. Many IDPs complaint that IDPs coming from Swat received treatment conforming to the principles of UNGPID, whereas FATA IDPs were maltreated by the authorities.(Ahmad, 2015)

Moreover, the UNGPID, principle 14 (1) and (2) also advocates about the right to the freedom of movement of IDPs not only within the state but if needed in and out of the state. It is also suggested that IDPs camps must be built in keeping in view their needs to transportation, food and health facilities. In 2009, it is reported that most camps were built in remote areas, which were miles away from the urban areas (Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) Operation in KP/FATA, 2014). It increased difficulties for the IDPs, as many when they were in need of health facility, being disappointed by the camp health care units, could not reach to the

hospitals in urban areas amid lack of transportation. Many reported that camps were built at places where there was no road infrastructure present, and a person in need to go to urban areas had to walk miles to access the vehicles. One of these camps was the Yar Hussain camp, which was 15 to 20 km away from Mardan, Swabi main road(Ahmad, 2015).

Besides, the humanitarian assistance according to United Nations human rights commission is not a narrow concept to merely include the food, shelter and health items to the IDPs, but it also covers the rights of IDPs to transportation, technology, and telecommunication to collect data pertinent to the losses they incurred and people they lost in the wake of crisis(Ahmad, 2015). However, for developing countries like Pakistan, where access to basic human needs to common people is difficult, governments rarely provides assistance in terms of provision of information technology and telecommunications.

And last but not the least, a defined national framework is required for IDPs to monitor the internally displaced children. Whenever a calamity hits or violence break out, a state of emergency occurs, in which there are fair chances that little children may be separated from their families. In Yar Hussain camp, many IDPs reported issues of their child being lost or died in the midst of the evacuation plan. Many children were also pushed by their families for child labor to increase their earnings, especially at camps which were located in close vicinity to the cities. There is a need to monitor internally displaced children's rights and develop a policy which discourages the trend of child labor and physical security(Ahmad, 2015).

Recommendations

Despite being a home to the persistent crisis of IDPs, national policy or long-term strategy is seen nowhere to address the issue of documented and un-documented IDPs. There is a need to strike a balance among fresh and old IDPs for the provision of supplies. As, whenever any conflict broke in any area, new IDPs grab attention, and old IDPs are out of sight and complexity increases because of the absence of a particular policy for IDPs. Although, there is no doubt that the government responded at their best to meet this menace, whenever there arose a need, lack of national policy pertinent to IDPs is a gap in the policy-making which needs to be filled at earliest.

It is also important to establish beforehand healthcare departments with sufficient female lady doctors and nurses to avoid any human loss. The mistakes once done in previous crisis must not be repeated. The future action plan must be revised to improve health care and nutrition facilities in the government run camps.

Provision of formal and informal technical education be provided to the people for a trivial period of time to avoid their educational loss. It is also government

responsibility to provide job opportunities to the IDPs, so they should not become a burden for the host areas but instead contribute positively to its economic fabric.

In the contemporary era, tents must be replaced with wooden camps or cottages. It is not difficult for governments to provide wooden camps to IDPs, in case of a break out of a crisis. A wooden camp can also save people from extreme hot and cold weather conditions. It will also be beneficial in resolving the issues related to the *Pardah* of the women belonging to any district. The government of Pakistan must develop a national framework for IDPs to avoid aforementioned issues in the future if in case any crisis or violent situation arises.

Conclusion

The displacement in the country has deprived millions of a decent way of living either directly or indirectly. Hundreds of thousands of affluent people live as homeless in their own country. Such deprivation is might push the displaced youth and children towards militancy as they these kinds of situations are usually breeding grounds for militancy. Another possibility is that the displaced youth and children might resort to mass movements against the government and military establishment because they have now, as result of their displacement to the settled areas, seen the level of development and have well gauged the level of deprivation in FATA against the advancement in settled areas. Therefore, the government should not only take appropriate measures for the quick return of the displaced people, but it should also take measures to provide them their constitutional rights during and after displacement to keep the desperate displaced youth and children of FATA away from agitations which are not in the interest of the state.

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